

BETANODAVIRUS VARIANTS CIRCULATING IN THE MEDITERRANEAN: A NOVEL, QUICK AND AFFORDABLE METHOD TO IDENTIFY GENOTYPES AND REASSORTANT STRAINS

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Introduction

Viral nervous necrosis (VNN) otherwise known as viral encephalopathy and retinopathy (VER), is the most threatening infectious disease in Mediterranean aquaculture. VNN is caused by the nervous necrosis virus (NNV) a bisegmented ssRNA⁺ virus included in the genus *Betanodavirus*, family *Nodaviridae*. NNV genome consists of two molecules named RNA1 and RNA2, which encodes for the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase and the coat protein, respectively. Four genotypes of NNV have been so far described: RGNNV, SJNNV, BFNNV, TPNNV (Sahul Hameed et al., 2019). Furthermore, reassortant strains have emerged from the reassortment between the RGNNV and the SJNNV genotypes and named RGNNV/SJNNV and SJNNV/RGNNV according to the RNA1 and RNA2 origin. Currently, several NNV strains are co-circulating in the Mediterranean Basin with a high prevalence of the RGNNV genotype and the RGNNV/SJNNV reassortant strain and a more limited diffusion of the SJNNV genotype and the SJNNV/RGNNV reassortant (Bandin and Souto, 2020; Volpe et al., 2020). So far, identification of NNV genotype and reassortant strains is based on amplification, sequencing and phylogenetic analysis of both viral genome RNA molecules requiring time and expertise. As viral identification is an essential information for the management of the disease in the field (Toffan et al., 2021), the development of an easy and affordable method to genotype betanodaviruses was developed in the framework of the H2020 Peformfish Project, an industry-driven project targeting industry defined priorities.

Materials and methods

RGNNV-RNA1, RGNNV-RNA2 and SJNNV-RNA2 specific primers were designed based on conserved regions within each genotype's sequences. The primer sets were selected according to their position within each genotype's RNA sequence, the melting temperature and the predicted amplicon size to amplify fragments of different sizes specific for RGNNV-RNA1, RGNNV-RNA2 and SJNNV-RNA2. After optimisation the novel multiplex RT-PCR assay was tested for analytical specificity and sensitivity and for repeatability through intra- and inter-assay variability tests. Furthermore, the diagnostic sensitivity and specificity was calculated using seventy-six samples including 50 European seabass and 23 gilthead sea bream brains and 3 *Artemia salina* (nauplii) samples and comparing the mRT-PCR to the OIE validated real-time RT-PCR taken as the "Gold Standard". The robustness of the method was assessed testing samples included in the third VER interlaboratory proficiency test (VER-IPT) organised by the OIE reference laboratory. Finally, the accuracy of the genotyping performed via the new developed mRT-PCR was assessed subjecting to the conventional genotyping a selection of positive samples which reported different range of results at the mRT-PCR assay.

Results

A one-step multiplex RT-PCR was developed to detect and simultaneously identify the presence of RGNNV, SJNNV or one of their reassortant strains through the amplification of a specific band pattern for each genotype/reassortant strain. No cross-reactivity with viruses and bacteria frequently associated with gilthead seabream, European seabass and marine environment was observed. The mRT-PCR showed a sensitivity ranging from $10^{2.3}$ to $10^{3.4}$ TCID₅₀ ml⁻¹ depending on the viral strain and a high repeatability with negative, weakly, and distinct positive samples. The mRT-PCR accurately detected no NNV-RNA in NNV-negative samples and produced at least one specific amplification band in all NNV-positive samples assuming a diagnostic specificity and sensitivity of 100%. The application of the mRT-PCR to the samples from the third VER-IPT enabled to correctly detect their positivity/negativity and to genotype them. Multiplex RT-PCR was able to assign to a genotype the RNA1 of all the positive samples and the RNA2 of 88% of positive samples.

Discussion and Conclusion

Several NNV strains are currently co-circulating in the Mediterranean Basin. Genotyping and reassortant identification are an essential information for the management of the disease in the field. However, proficiency tests performed by the OIE reference laboratory pointed out a limited capability to properly identify the NNV variants (Toffan et al., 2021). Identifying the genotypes and reassortant strains is so far based on traditional genotyping that consists in amplifying and sequencing of both viral genome RNA molecules. Only the analysis of both viral genome segments (RNA1 and RNA2) led to reassortant identification. This method is time-consuming and requires highly specialised staff and equipment, resulting in a limited number of laboratories able to perform a complete and correct viral species identification. The developed multiplex RT-PCR represents an easy, rapid, and affordable method to identify NNV variants circulating in the Mediterranean: RGNNV, SJNNV and the reassortant RGNNV/SJNNV and SJNNV/RGNNV strains. The method can find wide application in several sectors of the study of the VNN contributing to improve its knowledge and therefore leading to a better disease control. It can also be used for confirmatory diagnosis in NNV outbreaks in the Mediterranean increasing laboratories' capacity to correctly identify the betanodavirus genotype.

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